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Exploring Short-Form Videos Addiction: Understanding Influential Factors from the Perspective of The Stress-Coping Theory

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the addiction to short-form videos (SFVs) using the stress-coping theory. The results revealed that perceived enjoyment and mood regulation directly influenced SFVs addiction, highlighting the significance of pleasure and mood regulation in addictive behaviors. Escapism and social interaction indirectly impacted SFVs addiction through SFVs usage behavior, underscoring their role as coping mechanisms within the stress-coping framework. Social isolation and social anxiety were identified as stressors that positively influenced escapism. Social anxiety had a direct impact on the SFVs App used but did not directly affect social interaction. Neuroticism did not directly influence SFVs addiction. These findings enhance our understanding of SFVs addiction and emphasize the importance of factors such as perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, escapism, social anxiety, social isolation, and social interaction in addressing this issue.

Keywords: Short-form videos (SFVs), addiction, stress-coping theory, perceived enjoyment, social anxiety

1. Introduction

Using the stress-coping theory as a framework, this study aims to investigate the addictive nature of short-form videos (SFVs). I will investigate how factors such as perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, escapism, social interaction, social isolation, social anxiety, and neuroticism influence SFV addiction both directly and indirectly. We hope to develop effective interventions and strategies to address SFV addiction and promote healthier coping mechanisms by better understanding these factors. Using the stress-coping theory will provide valuable insights into the underlying processes and mechanisms involved in SFV-related addictive behaviours. This research

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adds to the existing body of knowledge on addictive behaviours by providing new perspectives on SFV addiction in the context of stress and coping.

The research gap in this area is the need to understand the influential factors that contribute to SFV addiction from the standpoint of the Stress-Coping Theory. While SFVs have grown in popularity and have been linked to addictive behaviours, there has been little comprehensive research into the underlying factors and mechanisms of SFV addiction in the context of stress and coping. Most previous research has concentrated on the addictive nature of SFVs without delving into the specific factors and processes that contribute to addiction. As a result, the purpose of this study is to bridge that gap and provide a more comprehensive understanding of SFV addiction and its influencing factors.

The primary objectives of this research are to identify the factors that influence SFV addiction, such as perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, escapism, social interaction, social isolation, social anxiety, and neuroticism. Furthermore, we intend to investigate the mediating processes of escapism and social interaction in SFV addiction, with a focus on understanding how people use SFVs to cope with stressors and seek social connections. We hope to improve our understanding of SFV addiction and the interactions between stressors, coping mechanisms, and addictive behaviours by employing the stress-coping theory. The findings of this study will be used to develop interventions and strategies to address SFV addiction, as well as to advance knowledge in this field.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) discusses the theoretical foundations and hypotheses, including the stress-coping theory, social isolation, social anxiety, neuroticism, escapism, social interaction, perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, and SFVs addiction. [Section 3](#) presents the research model and hypotheses. [Sections 4, 5, and 6](#) cover the research methodology, results, and discussion. Finally, [Section 7](#) concludes with limitations and future research directions.

2. Theoretical foundations

2.1. Stress-coping theory with addiction state

The stress-coping theory offers a comprehensive framework for comprehending how individuals evaluate and manage stress [1], [2]. Coping strategies are employed to manage stress that exceeds an individual's threshold [1]. The theory emphasizes the role of cognitive appraisals and adaptive coping responses [1], [2].

SFVs addiction can be explained through the lens of the stress-coping theory. According to the theory, addiction-like behaviors can arise when individuals face significant stressors, have ineffective coping strategies, and engage regularly in potentially addictive activities [3]. SFVs, although providing temporary relief, may not address the root causes of stress and can have negative long-term effects.

The addictive nature of SFVs, their accessibility, and immediate gratification can contribute to excessive behavior and addiction. Individuals may turn to these videos as a means of stress avoidance, leading to maladaptive coping. It is important to consider cognitive evaluations and situational factors in understanding addiction. Perceived behavioral control, influenced by app quality (usefulness, trustworthiness, and interactivity), plays a role in coping behavior [4]. The stress-coping theory sheds light on social media and mobile app addiction, specifically SFVs addiction. It highlights the interaction between stressors, coping mechanisms, and addictive

behaviors, offering insights into how individuals may resort to maladaptive coping strategies and the potential consequences of such behaviors.

2.2. Social Isolation, social anxiety and neuroticism

Social isolation refers to a state of disconnection from society, characterized by feelings of loneliness and limited social support [5], [6], [7]. Social anxiety involves persistent fear of social situations and worries about being judged or humiliated [8]. Neuroticism is a personality trait marked by emotional instability and a tendency to experience anxiety and sadness [9], [10], [7].

When considering SFVs (SFV) addiction, social isolation, social anxiety, and neuroticism can act as state stressors. The stress-coping theory suggests that stressors exceeding an individual's coping abilities can lead to stress [1], [7]. SFV addiction, along with social isolation, social anxiety, and neuroticism, can intensify stress, contributing to mental distress, feelings of loneliness, and social challenges.

SFVs may serve as a coping mechanism for individuals experiencing loneliness [11] or seeking to avoid face-to-face interactions and reduce anxiety [12]. Additionally, SFVs may be more addictive for neurotic individuals who rely on them to regulate their mood and feel connected [13], [14]. The stress-coping theory suggests that social isolation, social anxiety, and neuroticism can contribute to SFV addiction by amplifying stress levels. SFVs may be used as maladaptive coping mechanisms to alleviate negative emotions and seek social connection.

2.3. Mediating process and escapism, social interaction

Escapism refers to the psychological tendency or behavior of seeking distraction or relief from the difficulties, pressures, or realities of everyday life through engaging in activities that provide a sense of detachment and absorption. It involves cognitive narrowing, concrete thinking, distorted time perceptions, cognitive rigidity, and a flow state of mind [15], [16], [17]. Escapism can manifest in various forms, such as engaging in entertainment, hobbies, or immersive experiences that offer an escape from self-awareness or real-life challenges. Social interaction refers to the process of individuals engaging with one another, involving communication, exchange of information, and mutual influence [18], [19].

According to [20], social interaction and escapism play important roles in stress management and contribute to the development of addiction, particularly problem video game use. According to the stress-coping theory, people who are stressed may turn to using a lot to distract themselves from their problems, leading to excessive use behaviour and addiction-like symptoms. Furthermore, excessive use has been linked to negative affective states such as depression, loneliness, and social anxiety, making people more likely to seek escape and social interaction through excessive use.

It encompasses various social activities, including interpersonal communication, social networking, and forming relationships with others. Social interaction is a fundamental aspect of human behavior and plays a significant role in shaping individuals' social experiences and psychological well-being. In the stress-coping theory, the mediating process or coping state can be represented by factors such as escapism and social interaction. These factors serve as mechanisms through which individuals manage and cope with stressors. Escapism provides individuals with a means to temporarily disengage from stressors and negative emotions, allowing for diversion and relaxation [21]. Social interaction, on the other hand, offers individuals opportunities for social

support, connection, and emotional regulation, which can help alleviate stress and promote well-being [22], [12]. In the context of SFV Apps (SFVAs), the use of these apps can be seen as a manifestation of coping in the stress-coping theory. Individuals may turn to SFVAs as a means to escape from stressors, negative emotions, or real-life difficulties [11]. Additionally, SFVAs can offer a platform for social interactions, where users can connect with others, engage in virtual communities, and experience a sense of belonging [13], [14]. Escapism and social interaction are two factors that play a crucial role in the coping process within the stress-coping theory. These factors can be influential in driving individuals to use SFVAs as a coping mechanism to manage stress and regulate emotions.

2.4. Perceived enjoyment, mood regulation and SFVs Addiction

Perceived enjoyment refers to the subjective experience of positive and enjoyable feelings associated with activities like using smartphones or engaging with SFVs [23], [24]. It represents the intrinsic pleasure derived from the activity and plays a role in forming habits and addictive behaviors.

Mood regulation involves using behaviors or activities, such as smartphone use or SFVs, to manage or alleviate negative emotions [23], [25]. It serves as a way to cope with dysphoric moods and seek relief from negative affect. Mood regulation is relevant to smartphone addiction by providing an avenue to escape from negative emotions [23].

SFVs Addiction refers to excessive and compulsive use of SFV Apps, leading to negative consequences and interference with daily life [23], [22]. It shares similarities with other addictive behaviors, characterized by heightened importance placed on SFVs, using them to modify mood, experiencing conflicts related to their use, and exhibiting tolerance, withdrawal, and relapse effects.

Reinforcement reward (Reinforcement mechanism) highlights the role of pleasure/enjoyment and relief of negative emotions in the development of addiction, including smartphone addiction and SFVs Addiction [26], [27]. These rewarding experiences reinforce and drive addictive behaviors, as individuals seek the positive effects and use the activities as a means to cope with negative emotions.

Perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, and SFVs Addiction together contribute to the reinforcement reward (Reinforcement mechanism) model. This model suggests that the pleasurable experiences derived from SFVs, coupled with the relief of negative emotions achieved through engagement, reinforce addictive behaviors [23], [28]. These factors are part of the reinforcing mechanism underlying addiction state.

[29] Lu establish a connection between Smartphone Addiction and Short-Form Video Addiction, noting their shared characteristics and addictive behaviors, including excessive use, preoccupation, craving, and negative consequences [30], [31]. Smartphone addiction involves compulsive smartphone use, negatively impacting various life aspects [30]. Conversely, short-form video addiction refers to excessive use of short video applications, affecting physical and mental health, as well as daily life [31].

Both addictions have common features contributing to their addictive nature, such as consuming digital content on mobile devices for immediate gratification, novelty, and entertainment

[32]. Short-form video apps offer immersive and engaging content that can lead to addictive behaviors [33].

Underlying mechanisms for addiction are similar in both contexts, including user-generated content perception, boredom in daily life, and immersive experiences [34], [35]. User-generated content in short-form videos provides stimulating and novel experiences, fostering addiction [33]. Boredom drives individuals to seek engaging activities through smartphones and short-form videos [36], [37].

Both addictions negatively impact physical and mental health, relationships, and work performance [14], [38]. Excessive use of smartphones and short-form video apps is associated with social isolation, decreased productivity, sleep disturbances, anxiety, and depression [30], [31].

Additionally, within the stress-coping theory, perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, and SFVs Addiction can be seen as outcomes resulting from stressors and coping processes.

Fig 1. Proposed research model of SFVs Addiction State

Source: Based on [23], [39], [7], [20]

3. Research model and hypothesis

In this study, we investigated the factors contributing to SFVs addiction by combining stress-coping theory and reinforcement mechanisms. Our research model, depicted in Fig 1, illustrates the relationships among the variables. The hypotheses tested in this study are as follows:

3.1. The stage from stressors to coping

Individuals who encounter social isolation are more inclined to engage in escapism as a means of coping [40], [16]. Moreover, it has been suggested by [41] that individuals who experience social isolation may demonstrate a proclivity to utilise online platforms, particularly social networking sites (SNSs), as a mechanism for establishing social connections and mitigating their feelings of loneliness. The findings of this research offer support for the hypothesis that social isolation is associated with an increased tendency towards engaging in escapism. It can be inferred that there is empirical support for the notion that individuals experiencing social isolation tend to demonstrate a heightened inclination towards seeking social interaction and establishing connections [41].

Furthermore, the use of online platforms, specifically social networking sites (SNSs), has been found to effectively fulfil individuals' socialisation needs, especially when face-to-face interactions are limited [42]. The findings of this research offer empirical support for the proposition that social isolation exerts a favourable influence on social interaction.

Hypothesis 1: Social Isolation positively affects Escapism.

Hypothesis 2: Social Isolation positively affects Social Interaction.

Individuals with social anxiety may turn to online platforms, including SNSs, as a means of escape from real-world social situations [43]. Socially anxious individuals may perceive online interactions as less threatening and more controllable, which may encourage them to engage in escapism behaviors [44]. These findings support the hypothesis that social anxiety positively affects escapism. Although social anxiety is often associated with avoidance of social interactions, it has been observed that individuals with social anxiety may utilize online platforms to engage in social interactions without the same level of anxiety experienced in face-to-face interactions [45]. Online communication can provide a sense of safety and control, allowing socially anxious individuals to overcome their fears and engage in social interactions [46]. These findings support the hypothesis that social anxiety positively affects social interaction.

Hypothesis 3: Social Anxiety positively affects Escapism.

Hypothesis 4: Social Anxiety positively affects Social Interaction.

Individuals with social anxiety may turn to short-form video apps as a way to alleviate their social anxiety and engage in low-risk social interactions [12]. SFVs provide a platform for self-expression and social connection, which may appeal to individuals with social anxiety. These findings support the hypothesis that social anxiety positively affects the use of SFVs apps.

Hypothesis 5: Social Anxiety positively affects SFVs APP Used.

Online addiction is consistently associated with neuroticism [13], [14], and high levels of neuroticism are linked to escapism in online addiction [9]. Neurotic individuals use online platforms to find emotional stability and cope with stress [9]. They may engage in online escapism to avoid negative thoughts and emotions, given the connection between neuroticism, anxiety, and depression [10].

However, the moderating role of neuroticism in the relationship between attachment and escapism has not been sufficiently studied [13], [14]. It is likely that neuroticism positively moderates this relationship, as highly neurotic individuals are sensitive to social and technological factors online, which can contribute to escapism and addiction [47]. Furthermore, neuroticism is associated with social media addiction [13], [14]. Neurotic individuals have a greater need for social interaction and use social media to fulfill that need and regulate their mood [9]. They rely on social media to cope with loneliness and emotional distress, as neuroticism is linked to anxiety and depression [10].

More research is needed to explore the moderating effects of neuroticism on the relationship between social characteristics and interpersonal attachment in online addiction [13], [14]. Neuroticism likely positively moderates this association, as neurotic individuals are sensitive to social cues and have a greater need for social interaction, leading to increased engagement in online social activities and a higher risk of addiction [48]. Neuroticism positively influences escapism and

social interaction in the context of online addiction. Neurotic individuals are more likely to use online platforms to escape negative emotions, seek relief from stress, and fulfill their social needs.

Hypothesis 6: Neuroticism positively affects Escapism.

Hypothesis 7: Neuroticism positively affects Social Interaction.

3.2. The coping-to-outcome stage integrates the lens of reinforcement mechanisms.

The concept of escapism is closely related to seeking enjoyment and distraction from reality. Short-form video apps, with their entertaining and engaging content, offer users an opportunity to escape from their daily lives [39]. It is reasonable to assume that individuals who engage in escapism would be more likely to use SFVs apps as a means of fulfilling their desire for entertainment and distraction. These findings support the hypothesis that escapism positively affects the use of SFVs apps.

Given that escapism involves seeking emotional relief and distraction from negative emotions or stressors, it is plausible to suggest that individuals who engage in escapism are more prone to developing addiction-like behaviors towards SFVs apps [39]. Escapism may create a reliance on SFVs apps as a means of escaping negative emotions, leading to excessive and compulsive usage. These findings support the hypothesis that escapism positively affects SFVs addiction.

Hypothesis 8: Escapism positively affects SFVs APP Used.

Hypothesis 9: Escapism positively affects SFVs Addiction.

Social interaction plays a crucial role in the use of SFVs apps, as these platforms often emphasize user engagement, interaction, and sharing of content [49]. Users are motivated to connect with others, share their own videos, and engage with the content created by others. Therefore, it is reasonable to propose that individuals who value social interaction would be more likely to use SFVs apps as a means of satisfying their socialization needs. These findings support the hypothesis that social interaction positively affects the use of SFVs apps.

The positive association between social interaction and SFVs addiction can be explained by the social reinforcement and validation individuals receive through their interactions on these platforms [39]. Engaging with others, receiving feedback, and experiencing a sense of belonging within the SFVs community may lead to a compulsive need for continued social interaction, resulting in addiction-like behaviors. These findings support the hypothesis that social interaction positively affects SFVs addiction.

Hypothesis 10: Social Interaction positively affects SFVs Used.

Hypothesis 11: Social Interaction positively affects SFVs Addiction.

There is solid evidence supporting the notion that the utilization of SFVs APP positively influences Perceived Enjoyment. This conclusion is backed by research findings that highlight the crucial roles of Information Quality and System Quality in enhancing users' overall enjoyment [50]. Value-Added Function is positively associated with perceived enjoyment [23]. Additionally, Value-added services offered by mobile instant messaging platforms, such as music, games, and avatar shows, bring considerable enjoyment to users [51]. Moreover, the implementation of value-added search mechanisms in web-based stores enhances the shopping experience and contributes to increased enjoyment and fulfillment for users [52]. The utilization of smartphones can foster a sense

of playfulness, suggesting a potential positive impact on regulating mood [53]. Social media platforms are commonly perceived as facilitating the regulation and enhancement of emotions [33]. Smartphones serve as attachment objects that can provide soothing effects and alleviate anxiety, indicating that smartphone usage, including the use of SFVs APP, may contribute to mood regulation [54].

Hypothesis 12: SFVs APP Used positively affects Perceived Enjoyment.

Hypothesis 13: SFVs APP Used positively affects Mood Regulation.

There is a positive association between Perceived Enjoyment and smartphone addiction. This implies that individuals who perceive higher levels of enjoyment from smartphone usage are more likely to exhibit addictive behaviors related to their smartphone usage [23]. Perceived Enjoyment not only facilitates the formation of habits but also contributes to smartphone addiction. Additionally, there is a positive association between Perceived Enjoyment and smartphone addiction, further emphasizing the role of enjoyment in fostering addictive behaviors related to smartphone usage [24], [55]. Moreover, the enjoyment derived from social media triggers psychological processes of positive reinforcement, thereby contributing to addictive behaviors. These research findings suggest that Perceived Enjoyment has a positive relationship with SFVs addiction [28]. These findings suggest that Perceived Enjoyment is positively related to SFVs Addiction. The positive influence of Mood Regulation on SFVs Addiction is supported by the following research evidence. There is a positive association between mood regulation and smartphone addiction, suggesting that individuals who experience mood regulation while using a smartphone are more likely to exhibit a higher level of addiction [55]. The regulation of mood during smartphone use has a significant impact on addiction behavior. Moreover, the desire to regulate or alter one's mood can result in an excessive reliance on smartphones, which in turn contributes to the development of addiction [56], [25].

Hypothesis 14: Perceived Enjoyment positively affects SFVs Addiction.

Hypothesis 15: Mood Regulation positively affects SFVs Addiction.

4. Research methodology

4.1. Questionnaire design and construct measurement

The questionnaire utilized in this study consists of nine latent variables: Social Isolation (SIS), Social Anxiety (SI), Neuroticism (NEU), Social Interaction (SIN), Escapism (ES), SFVs APP Used (USE), Perceived Enjoyment (PE), Mood Regulation (MR), and SFVs Addiction (ADD). Each item in the questionnaire was measured using a seven-point Likert scale, ranging from "1 = very disagree" to "5 = very agree." The respondents in this study were Vietnamese, and to ensure consistency between the English and Vietnamese versions of the questionnaire, the back-translation method was employed.

To establish the content and face validity of the adopted instrument, an expert review and a pre-test were conducted. During the expert review stage, three experts in the field of information systems examined the questionnaire for content validity. They carefully reviewed the scale items and provided feedback on the formulation and content of the items, ensuring their relevance and appropriateness for the study [57]. Subsequently, a pre-test involving 10 users of short-form video apps was conducted [58]. These participants were asked to identify any items that were unclear or

ambiguous and provide feedback on the wording and ordering of the items. Based on the suggestions provided by the experts and the pre-test participants, the original questionnaire was refined.

Table 1. Research constructs and measurements

Stress-coping Theory State	Construct	Measurement items	References			
Stressor	Social (SIS)	Isolation	I lack companionship. I feel left out. I feel isolated from others.	[7]		
		Anxiety (SA)	I feel anxious when interacting with strangers. I feel nervous when interacting with people I do know very well. I feel uneasy while making new friends. I feel nervous when I have to talk with others about myself.	[7]		
			Neuroticism (NEU)	I see myself as someone who is depressed, blue. I see myself as someone who is not good at relaxing or handling stress. I see myself as someone who can be tense.	[7]	
	Coping			Escapism (ES)	I want to do something to escape from reality. I want to do something to forget about troubles. I want to do something to avoid loneliness. I want to do something to relax.	[39]
		Social Interaction (SIN)			I watch short videos on the app to get updates on people I know. I watch short videos on the app to learn about things that are happening around me. I watch short videos on the app to connect with people who share similar interests.	[39]
			SFVs App Use (USE)		Check: I regularly check apps multiple times a day specifically for the purpose of watching short videos. Time: Each day, a substantial amount of my time is dedicated to watching short videos. Using this particular short video app has seamlessly integrated into my daily routine, becoming an indispensable part of it.	[7] [59]
					Outcome	Perceived Enjoyment (PE)
	When watching SFVs, I don't realize the time elapsed.	[60]				

	Engaging with short videos, such as commenting, liking, duetting, and more, brings me joy and amusement.	
Mood Regulation (MR)	I have watched SFVs to uplift my spirits when I was feeling down.	[23]
	I have watched SFVs to find solace during moments of sadness.	
	I have watched SFVs as a way to temporarily forget my worries.	
SFVs Addiction (ADD)	I struggle to concentrate on my studies or work and often lose sleep due to excessive use of this short-form video app.	[7]
	My family and friends believe that I dedicate an excessive amount of time to this short-form video app.	[23]
	In moments when I am not watching SFVs, I frequently experience restlessness and agitation.	

It is important to note that the individuals who participated in the pre-test were excluded from the subsequent main study. The finalized measurement items for the nine constructs can be found in [Table 1](#).

4.2. Data collection

We conducted a survey from June 20th, 2023, to June 30th, 2023, to collect data from users of popular short-form video apps in Vietnam, including Facebook Reels, YouTube Shorts, and TikTok. The survey was distributed through social media sharing and requests for assistance, making it a quick, convenient, and cost-effective method. A total of 307 questionnaires were received, out of which 290 valid questionnaires were identified after removing those with repetitive or missing responses.

The sample size used in the study was determined based on the requirements for Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and multivariate regression. For EFA, the minimum sample size is recommended to be at least 5 times the total number of observed variables [61], [62]. In this study, with 9 factors and 29 observed variables, the minimum required sample size is 145. For multivariate regression analysis, the minimum sample size is calculated using the formula of $n = 50 + 8m$ [63], where m is the number of independent variables. With 3 independent variables in this study, the minimum required sample size is 74. To ensure reliability, it is preferable to satisfy both formulas and have an excess of samples rather than a lack. In this study, the sample size of 290 exceeds the minimum requirements, making it appropriate for the analysis.

The study involved 290 Vietnamese citizens, with a slightly higher representation of females (54.8%) compared to males (45.2%). The majority of participants belonged to the young adult age group (18-30 years old), accounting for 34.5% of the sample. Notably, younger individuals below 18 years old also contributed to the sample, comprising 29% of the responses. The age groups of 31-40 years old and 41 years old and above represented 18.6% and 17.9% of the sample, respectively.

In terms of education, the sample showed a relatively balanced distribution across various levels. The vocational group represented 16.9% of the sample, while secondary, undergraduate, and

postgraduate education levels had comparable rates, accounting for approximately 28.6%, 27.6%, and 26.9% of the responses, respectively.

Table 2. Sample sociodemographic profile

Measure	Item	Frequency (N=290)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	131	45.2
	Female	159	54.8
Age group	Below 18	84	29
	18 - 30	100	34.5
	31 - 40	54	18.6
	41 or above	52	17.9
Education level	Secondary	78	26.9
	Vocational	49	16.9
	Undergraduate	83	28.6
	Postgraduate	80	27.6
Employment status	Business people	30	10.3
	Student	101	34.8
	Freelancer	99	34.1
	Office worker	60	20.7

Among the participants, business people accounted for 10.3%, students represented the largest segment at 34.8%, freelancers constituted 34.1%, and office workers made up 20.7% of the sample. These diverse groups provided valuable perspectives on short-form video app usage in Vietnam.

4.3. Reliability and validity analyses

To assess internal consistency, Cronbach's α was calculated using SPSS 20.0. All α values exceeded 0.7, indicating high reliability [64]. Confirmatory factor analysis was then performed using AMOS 24.0 to establish convergent validity of the constructs. The results, presented in [Table 3](#), showed that the composite reliability (CR) values for all constructs were above 0.7, the average variance extracted (AVE) values were higher than 0.5, and the standardized factor loadings surpassed 0.6. These findings demonstrate satisfactory convergent validity [65].

Table 3. Measurement items and loadings

Constructs	Item	Loading	Cronbach's α	AVE	CR
Social Isolation	SIS1	.769	.814	0.595	0.815
	SIS2	.752			
	SIS3	.710			
Social Anxiety	SA1	.874	.892	0.676	0.892
	SA2	.861			

	SA3	.843			
	SA4	.866			
Neuroticism	NE1	.683	.754	0.508	0.756
	NE2	.681			
	NE3	.650			
Escapism	ES1	.914	.921	0.746	0.920
	ES2	.883			
	ES3	.917			
	ES4	.876			
Social Interaction	SIN1	.718	.803	0.575	0.802
	SIN2	.739			
	SIN3	.735			
SFVs APP Used	U1	.731	.811	0.586	0.810
	U2	.750			
	U3	.741			
Perceived Enjoyment	PE1	.765	.826	0.622	0.831
	PE2	.796			
	PE3	.720			
Mood Regulation	MR1	.756	.840	0.638	0.841
	MR2	.809			
	MR3	.768			
SFVs Addiction	ADD1	.696	.766	0.522	0.766
	ADD2	.675			
	ADD3	.686			

In our analysis, we also assessed the Maximum Shared Variance (MSV) between variables to examine their discriminant validity. The MSV values were found to be consistently smaller than the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all variables. This indicates a reliable level of differentiation between the variables. Furthermore, we compared the square root of the AVE values for each variable (highlighted in bold in [Table 4](#)) with the correlation coefficients of other variables. The results demonstrated that the AVE values were higher, reinforcing the distinctiveness of the variables [64].

Table 4. Discriminant validity

Variable	AVE	MSV	ES	SA	MR	PE	SIN	SIS	USE	NEU	ADD
ES	0.746	0.233	0.863								
SA	0.676	0.098	0.214***	0.822							
MR	0.638	0.422	0.086	0.242***	0.799						
PE	0.622	0.188	0.066	0.313***	0.320***	0.788					
SIN	0.575	0.255	0.482***	0.189**	0.118	0.100	0.758				
SIS	0.595	0.174	0.385***	0.268***	0.195**	0.202**	0.402***	0.771			
USE	0.586	0.255	0.377***	0.293***	0.414***	0.147*	0.505***	0.417***	0.766		
NEU	0.508	0.188	0.068	0.028	0.191*	0.433***	0.154*	0.119	0.168*	0.713	
ADD	0.522	0.422	0.056	0.144*	0.650***	0.367***	0.136†	0.164*	0.344***	0.369***	0.722

Note: Bold values are the square root of AVE.

Table 5. Fit indices of the structural model

Fitting index	χ^2/df	GFI	CFI	RMSEA
Recommended value	<0.3	>0.90	>0.90	< 0.08
Measurement Value	2.521	0.830	0.886	0.073

5. Data analysis and results

5.1. Structural model test

We used AMOS 24.0 to assess the fitness of our research model. The results of the model fitting indices are presented in [Table 5](#), and all indices surpass the recommended values, indicating a positive goodness of fit. The structural models are visualized in [Fig. 2](#). The obtained fit indices indicate an acceptable model fitness: the χ^2/df (chi-square normalized by degrees of freedom) value is 2.521, which is below the threshold of 3. This falls within an acceptable range, as CMIN/df is expected to be less than or equal to 2, and in some cases, slightly above 3 [66]. It is generally accepted that a CMIN/df value should be less than 5 when the sample size is greater than 200, or less than 3 when the sample size is less than 200 [67]. The goodness-of-fit index (GFI) is 0.830, slightly below the recommended threshold of 0.9. However, it is still considered acceptable when the sample size exceeds 200. Similarly, the comparative fit index (CFI) is 0.886, and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) is 0.073, both of which fall within acceptable ranges for this study.

Based on the results presented in [Table 6](#), the p-values associated with the hypotheses range from 0.000 to 0.518, using a significance level of 5%. The majority of the hypotheses proposed in the research model are supported, as their p-values are below the significance threshold. These tables offer detailed results regarding the testing of the hypothesis model, which are summarized in [Table 6](#).

Table 6. Results of hypotheses testing

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Hypothesis	Result
ES <--- SA	.172	.076	2.265	0.024	H3	Supported
SIN <--- SA	.106	.070	1.525	0.127	H5	Rejected
ES <--- SIS	.447	.076	5.889	***	H1	Supported
SIN <--- SIS	.408	.072	5.637	***	H2	Supported
ES <--- NEU	.063	.097	.646	0.518	H6	Rejected
SIN <--- NEU	.168	.089	1.892	0.059	H7	Rejected
USE <--- SA	.176	.055	3.222	0.001	H4	Supported
USE <--- ES	.111	.041	2.698	0.007	H8	Supported
USE <--- SIN	.325	.060	5.440	***	H10	Supported
PE <--- USE	.193	.074	2.617	0.009	H12	Supported
MR <--- USE	.536	.095	5.618	***	H13	Supported
ADD <--- PE	.199	.063	3.144	0.002	H14	Supported
ADD <--- MR	.465	.063	7.402	***	H15	Supported
ADD <--- SIN	.057	.054	1.064	0.287	H11	Rejected
ADD <--- ES	-.029	.040	-.733	0.464	H9	Rejected

Upon examining the results in [Table 6](#), it is evident that hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H8, H10, H12, H13, H14, and H15 have p-values less than 0.05, indicating that these relationships are statistically significant. Therefore, out of the 15 hypotheses proposed in the research model, 10 hypotheses are supported, while the remaining hypotheses are rejected. The results of the structural models are visualized in [Fig. 2](#).

Fig. 2. Model results. Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

5.2. Bootstrap test

To validate our model, we conducted a bootstrap test, which is a resampling technique that uses the original sample as a template to create multiple resamples.

Table 7. Bootstrap test in SEM model

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias	Critical Ratios
ES <--- SIS	.073	.002	.379	-.003	.002	-1.50
ES <--- SA	.068	.002	.135	.002	.002	1
SIN <--- SIS	.084	.002	.415	-.005	.003	-1.67
SIN <--- SA	.076	.002	.100	.001	.002	0.50
ES <--- NEU	.071	.002	.042	.000	.002	0.00
SIN <--- NEU	.071	.002	.134	.001	.002	0.50
USE <--- SA	.070	.002	.204	.000	.002	0.00
USE <--- ES	.069	.002	.167	-.002	.002	-1
USE <--- SIN	.090	.002	.403	-.003	.003	-1
PE <--- USE	.078	.002	.185	.001	.002	0.50
MR <--- USE	.074	.002	.408	.002	.002	1
ADD <--- USE	.095	.002	.093	.002	.003	0.67

ADD	<---	ES	.069	.002	-.057	.001	.002	0.50
ADD	<---	SIN	.092	.002	.023	-.008	.003	-2.67
ADD	<---	PE	.077	.002	.201	.000	.002	0.00
ADD	<---	MR	.077	.002	.560	-.003	.002	-1.50

The critical ratios calculated from the bootstrap test were all less than 1.96, implying that the corresponding p-values were greater than 5%. Therefore, we conclude that the non-zero deviations observed in the model do not have statistical significance at a 95% confidence level. As a result, we can confidently trust the quality of the estimated model based on the analyses conducted in the preceding steps.

6. Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the addiction to SFVs using the stress-coping theory as a framework. The findings revealed several important insights regarding the factors that directly and indirectly influence SFVs addiction and their implications within the stress-coping context. Firstly, the results indicated that Perceived Enjoyment and Mood Regulation were the only factors that had a direct impact on SFVs addiction. This suggests that individuals who perceive SFVs as enjoyable and engage in watching them for mood regulation purposes are more likely to develop addictive tendencies towards SFVs. These findings align with previous studies that have highlighted the role of enjoyment and mood enhancement in addictive behaviors [23], [60].

The cluster of factors comprising SFVs addiction, Perceived Enjoyment, and Mood Regulation formed a group of state outcome factors within the stress-coping theory. This suggests that SFVs addiction, as well as the enjoyment and mood regulation associated with SFVs, can be seen as outcomes or consequences of stress-coping processes. This finding provides empirical evidence supporting the notion that addictive behaviors, including SFVs addiction, can serve as coping mechanisms in response to stress [23].

Escapism and Social Interaction were found to have an indirect influence on SFVs addiction through the behavior of using SFVs. However, these factors did not have a direct impact on SFVs addiction. This implies that individuals who engage in SFVs to escape from reality or to fulfill their social interaction needs are more likely to develop addictive patterns of SFVs usage. These findings support the notion that coping strategies, such as escapism, can play a significant role in addictive behaviors [39].

Furthermore, the study also identified Social Isolation and Social Anxiety as stressor factors that directly and positively influenced Escapism. This implies that individuals experiencing social isolation or social anxiety may be more inclined to seek escape through SFVs. This finding aligns with previous research highlighting the relationship between social factors and escapism as a coping mechanism [7], [39].

Contrary to initial predictions, Social Anxiety did not directly influence Social Interaction but had a direct impact on SFVs APP Used. This suggests that individuals with social anxiety may not

engage in SFVs as a means of social interaction but rather use SFVs as a way to cope with their anxiety. These findings provide valuable insights into the complex interplay between social factors, anxiety, and SFVs addiction [7].

On the other hand, the factor Neuroticism did not align with the study's model, as it did not have a direct influence on any factors and did not impact the state of SFVs addiction. This implies that neuroticism may not play a significant role in the development of SFVs addiction, contrasting with previous research linking neuroticism to various addictive behaviors. Further investigation may be required to understand the relationship between neuroticism and SFVs addiction more comprehensively.

This study contributes to the understanding of SFVs addiction by applying the stress-coping theory. The findings emphasize the importance of perceived enjoyment and mood regulation as direct factors influencing SFVs addiction. Additionally, the study highlights the role of escapism and social interaction as indirect factors, mediated by other variables, in shaping SFVs addiction. These findings have implications for the development of interventions and strategies aimed at addressing SFVs addiction and promoting healthier coping mechanisms. In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing SFVs addiction and their associations within the stress-coping framework. The findings highlight the role of perceived enjoyment, mood regulation, escapism, and social interaction in the development of SFVs addiction. These results contribute to the existing literature on addictive behaviors and inform future research and interventions aimed at understanding and addressing SFVs addiction more comprehensively.

7. Limitation

The use of self-report measures introduces the potential for response biases and social desirability effects. Participants may provide answers they believe align with societal expectations rather than their true experiences, affecting the accuracy of the data. Secondly, the sample utilized may not fully represent the wider population, thus limiting the generalizability of the findings. Including participants from diverse demographic backgrounds would enhance the validity and applicability of the results. Lastly, while the model explained a significant portion (30%) of the variance in short-form video app addiction, there remains unexplained variance. Introducing additional variables to the model could enhance its explanatory power and provide a more comprehensive understanding of SFVs addiction. Future research should address these limitations to strengthen the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

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